

Research Article

Systematic Literature Review on Teaching Children Through Storytelling Techniques in the Classroom

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Abstract: *Teaching through storytelling techniques has been recognized as an effective educational method for children. Storytelling, as an art that involves narrative, imagination, and expression, not only captivates students' attention but also aids in the learning process. This study aims to identify storytelling techniques for teaching children in the classroom. Specifically, it examines how storytelling can influence moral understanding, cultural appreciation, and health behaviors among preschool and elementary school children. The research method employed is qualitative, utilizing the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) approach. This study involves the selection and analysis of 27 articles from databases such as ERIC, Scopus, and Google Scholar. The article selection process follows the PRISMA methodology, including stages of screening, exclusion, and eligibility based on specific criteria. Data were analyzed by extracting key information such as publication year, research objectives, methodology, sample, and main findings from the selected articles. The findings of the study indicate that most articles on storytelling techniques in the classroom were published between 2018 and 2021, with a decline in 2022 and 2023. The sample articles also show that most research focused on preschool-aged children. Storytelling has a positive impact on the development of academic, affective, and health aspects of students and can play a significant role in enhancing understanding and appreciation of cultural heritage.*

Keywords: storytelling; education; children

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1. INTRODUCTION

Child development is a crucial stage that should not be neglected by adults. It is closely related to education, which plays an essential role in fostering various aspects of a child's growth. In this context, these aspects include cognitive, physical-motor, language development, the formation of religious and moral values, as well as artistic development in a holistic manner (Naldi, 2018). Consequently, all these aspects are considered primary goals in ensuring the success of early learning processes among children today. Additionally, each of these aspects is emphasized within the learning curriculum (Akbar & Abidin, 2018).

Therefore, storytelling, whether in traditional or digital form, is a literacy tool frequently used by teachers to engage pupils interactively in the classroom. Moreover, it helps pupils connect academic content with their personal experiences (Sani & Yunus, 2018). Specifically, storytelling methods are often used to explain or narrate ideas, concepts, or history in an engaging and easily understandable way for listeners, including schoolchildren today (Ariffin, 2018). The storytelling process involves the absorption of knowledge conveyed by the storyteller to the listeners. Children who listen to stories not

only gain knowledge but also experience enjoyment, as stories are often delivered in an entertaining manner (Fitriani & Iiyas, 2021).

However, teachers face challenges when using storytelling techniques in teaching and learning. Problems often arise when teachers have difficulty understanding the speech patterns of children from diverse cultural backgrounds. As a result, the delivery of lessons cannot be carried out effectively. The teacher's storytelling technique significantly influences children's learning, particularly those from different backgrounds. The use of limited and inappropriate techniques that do not align with children's developmental stages affects their comprehension and prevents them from responding optimally to the teacher (Aishah & Mohd Nazri, 2019).

Thus, implementing storytelling techniques in the classroom is highly relevant, and research is needed to provide more in-depth information for practitioners and researchers. Through this study, we can closely examine the effects of storytelling techniques in children's education. In other words, this research will help answer fundamental questions regarding trends and outcomes of storytelling methods. It will also provide a general overview of the existing evidence in this field, which can help shape the direction of future research. Moreover, it is undeniable that the implications of this study are closely linked to the field of educational technology in the modern era. Therefore, to ensure the success of this study, we introduce a review method, followed by comprehensive findings and discussions later.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Storytelling Methods

Storytelling has long been an essential tool in communication and education. Stories serve not only as a medium for conveying information but also as an effective means of connecting people, cultures, and generations. Storytelling enables individuals to share experiences, knowledge, and values in an engaging and easily understandable manner.

In the educational context, storytelling plays a crucial role in enhancing learning, encouraging pupil engagement, and strengthening cognitive and social skills (Bruner, 1991). Storytelling methods can be categorized into two main types: traditional storytelling and digital storytelling.

Traditional storytelling refers to techniques that have been used for centuries, such as oral narration, facial expressions, body language, and storytelling aids like puppets and pictures. Traditional storytelling helps develop children's imagination, comprehension, and early literacy skills. However, this method faces challenges in maintaining audience interest and attention, especially in today's fast-paced digital era (Jariah et al., 2022).

On the other hand, digital storytelling is a more modern approach that integrates digital media elements such as text, images, audio recordings, music, and videos to deliver stories. Digital storytelling provides opportunities to create more interactive and engaging learning experiences, allowing children to actively participate in the storytelling process. By using digital devices, children can make choices, complete tasks, and interact with characters and story environments, ultimately enhancing their learning experience (Ikmal, 2021).

2.2 Traditional Storytelling

Traditional storytelling is an enjoyable and effective method for capturing interest across different audiences at any time. Stories enhance learning, strengthen intergenerational connections, and

reinforce cultural uniqueness and identity. They also help individuals navigate modern-day challenges (Fadzli et al., 2024). Traditional storytelling has long been used as a powerful communication tool to convey ideas, concepts, or historical narratives in an engaging and easily understandable manner (Jariah et al., 2022).

However, a major challenge in traditional storytelling is maintaining audience interest and attention, particularly in educational settings where teachers must compete with various technological distractions. Additionally, the effectiveness of traditional storytelling in learning depends on an individual's storytelling skills, which may vary among teachers. This highlights the need for specialized training to help educators effectively integrate storytelling into their classrooms (Hamzah et al., 2018).

Various storytelling techniques, such as facial expressions, body language, voice intonation, and storytelling aids, can be used to engage children and ensure they comprehend the message being conveyed. These techniques also foster children's imagination, enhance comprehension, and support early literacy development more effectively (Rahman et al., 2019). However, the success of these techniques depends on a teacher's ability to master and integrate them into their teaching strategies (Hamzah et al., 2018).

Recent studies indicate that traditional storytelling remains relevant in modern learning environments and can be combined with digital technology to create a more comprehensive learning experience (Fadzli et al., 2024). Although digital storytelling is becoming increasingly popular, traditional storytelling remains a vital tool in early literacy development and the preservation of cultural identity.

2.3 Digital Storytelling

Digital storytelling is an art form that combines traditional storytelling with digital media elements such as text, images, audio recordings, music, and videos. Most digital stories are short, typically lasting between 2 to 10 minutes, and are stored in digital formats that can be viewed on computers or other devices capable of playing video files. Additionally, digital stories are often uploaded to the internet, making them accessible via popular web browsers (Robin, 2016).

Digital storytelling is becoming increasingly popular among children in modern classrooms, as it actively engages them in the storytelling process through digital devices. However, the use of this technology also presents certain challenges. For example, there is a risk of overdependence on digital devices, which may reduce children's social interactions and physical skills (Ikmal, 2021). Therefore, this approach must be implemented carefully and in a balanced manner to ensure that it provides maximum benefits without causing unintended negative effects.

Furthermore, children engaging with digital storytelling often interact with devices by selecting appropriate actions, completing tasks, and engaging with main characters and environments. This process can indirectly enhance their reading experience and learning engagement (Ikmal, 2021). However, the long-term effects of this technology on children's cognitive and emotional development require further in-depth research. There are concerns that excessive screen time could lead to health issues such as eye strain and sleep disturbances.

In addition, digital storytelling is an innovative practice that allows pupils to engage more deeply with content while promoting critical thinking and technological skills. While the benefits of digital storytelling are widely recognized, it is also essential to consider the variations in its effectiveness based on pupils' cultural and socio-economic contexts. Further research is needed to understand how these factors influence learning outcomes (Mustaffa & Ghani, 2020).

According to Mustaffa and Ghani (2020), digital storytelling can be applied in education to enable collaborative learning between teachers and pupils. This approach has the potential to enrich learning experiences, but it also requires adequate training and support for teachers to ensure they can effectively use the technology. A lack of training and support may limit the effectiveness of digital storytelling in education.

At the same time, digital stories are considered a pupil-centered approach that enhances the learning environment by integrating key elements such as text, images, videos, and music (Ayob et al., 2022). However, further research is necessary to determine the long-term impact of digital storytelling on learning outcomes. Moreover, it is crucial to ensure that digital story content is of high quality and appropriate for pupils' needs and developmental stages.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The research method employed in this study is qualitative, using the Systematic Literature Review (SLR) approach. SLR is a structured and systematic methodology used to assess and synthesize previous studies in a thorough manner. This approach was chosen because it provides a comprehensive overview of the topic under study based on valid and widely accepted evidence (Petticrew & Roberts, 2006).

3.2 Research Procedure

The first step in SLR is formulating clear and specific research questions. These questions will serve as a guide in searching and evaluating literature. The research questions must be relevant to the studied topic and formulated objectively (Kitchenham & Charters, 2007). The literature search is conducted through recognized databases such as Scopus, Google Scholar, and ERIC. This search uses keywords relevant to the research topic, including technical terms, synonyms, and related phrases (Tranfield, Denyer, & Smart, 2003). The screening process is carried out to select studies that meet the inclusion and exclusion criteria that have been set. Inclusion criteria include studies published within a specific period (2018-2023), using certain methodologies, or relevant to the research question. Exclusion criteria involve studies that are not relevant, lack sufficient data, or are of low quality (Moher et al., 2009).

Each selected study undergoes a quality assessment using an appropriate evaluation tool, such as PRISMA. This assessment aims to ensure that only high-quality studies are considered in the next analysis. The aspects assessed include research design, sample size, accuracy of analysis, and data reliability (Higgins & Green, 2011). Data from the selected studies will be extracted and systematically arranged. The extracted data includes information about research methodology, study samples, findings, and conclusions. This data extraction process is conducted meticulously to ensure accuracy and consistency in the collected data (Booth, Sutton, & Papaioannou, 2016).

The extracted data will be synthesized to provide a comprehensive overview of the studied topic. Data synthesis is performed narratively or using statistical techniques such as meta-analysis, depending on the type and amount of collected data. This synthesis aims to identify patterns, trends, and key findings from previous studies (Munn et al., 2018). The SLR reporting process involves discussing the main findings, research implications, and recommendations for future research. The report should also include any limitations identified during the research process (PRISMA, 2024).

3.3 Search Strategy

This study employs the SLR approach to evaluate and synthesize previous research on education through storytelling for children. This approach is structured and evidence-based, aiming to provide a comprehensive overview of the studied topic. The three main databases used are ERIC, Scopus, and Google Scholar, selected based on their reliability and extensive coverage of published research in the field of education (Mayr & Walter, 2007).

The keyword used is "storytelling techniques in children's education," chosen because it is specific and relevant to the research topic. The PRISMA method is applied to ensure the SLR process is conducted systematically and meticulously, involving the collection and screening of article sources, as well as the selection of eligibility and exclusion criteria (Moher et al., 2009).

3.4 Sources

The article search process is conducted through three main databases: ERIC, Scopus, and Google Scholar. Each of these databases has its own characteristics and advantages in searching for high-quality scholarly literature. Google Scholar, launched in 2004, offers a very broad and easily accessible search for scholarly literature (Mayr & Walter, 2007). Scopus, also launched in 2004, is the largest database for research literature, providing abstracts and citations from various high-quality journals (Burnham, 2006). ERIC provides access to educational literature and resources, managed by the Institute of Education Sciences (IES) under the U.S. Department of Education (Sugimoto et al., 2011).

3.5 PRISMA

PRISMA, short for Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses, is a widely used guideline in systematic research and meta-analysis to ensure transparency and completeness in reporting. This guideline helps researchers collect, filter, and report research findings systematically and transparently (Moher et al., 2009).

3.6 Eligibility and Exclusion Criteria

Journal articles selected for this SLR must meet specific criteria. Review articles, books, book series, and book chapters are not prioritized. The search process focuses on publications in Malay and English from the years 2018 to 2024. Only articles related to "Storytelling Education" in the context of education are prioritized, regardless of the country of study origin.

Table 1. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Criteria	Inclusion	Exclusion
Document Type	Journal articles	Review articles, books, book series, and book chapters
Language	Malay and English	Languages other than Malay and English
Publication Timeline	2018 – 2023	<2018

3.7 Article Selection Process

The article selection process for the literature review was conducted in May 2024. Figure 1 illustrates the article selection flowchart adapted from the PRISMA flowchart. At the Identification stage, keywords for the search process were identified. Based on previous studies, the same and related keywords for Storytelling Education were used as stated. A total of 698 similar articles were found at this stage. In the Eligibility stage, 366 out of 698 articles were excluded. The exclusion was based on non-article types, publication timeline selection, and article availability. At the Screening stage, full articles were reviewed. After a thorough examination, 305 articles were excluded because they were not relevant and did not focus on Storytelling Education. Finally, a total of 27 articles were included for review and qualitative analysis.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the Article Selection Process

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS

4.1 Analysis of Article Publication Years

From the analysis of existing article publication years, the frequency pattern of articles can be illustrated as follows:

Table 2. Analysis of Article Publication Years

Publication Year	Article Numbers
2018	2, 4, 5, 6, 15, 21
2019	3, 12, 19, 22, 27

Publication Year	Article Numbers
2020	7, 17, 20, 25, 26
2021	1, 11, 14, 16, 18, 24
2022	8, 10, 23
2023	9, 13

In summary, the majority of articles (11 out of 27 articles) were published between 2018 and 2019. This indicates a stable increase in publications over the years, reflecting a consistent interest in this research topic during that period. However, a decline occurred in 2022 and 2023. 2018 and 2021 were the years with the highest number of articles published, suggesting a strong focus on publication during those periods. The increase in those years may have been driven by growing awareness of the importance of the research topic or the emergence of new technologies enabling more in-depth studies.

Conversely, the decline in 2022 and 2023 may have resulted from shifts in research priorities, limited funding resources, or a transition to other research topics. The impact of this trend suggests that while there was high interest in certain years, variability exists, requiring further attention. Researchers need to consider the factors influencing publication trends and explore ways to ensure sustained interest and continuous research in this field.

4.2 Analysis of Sample Articles

It cannot be denied that children greatly enjoy listening to stories, and through storytelling, they give their full attention to every word conveyed by the storyteller (Nurhayati et al., 2022). This storytelling-based pedagogical approach can aid in the cognitive, affective, and psychomotor development of pupils. Therefore, recognizing the benefits of storytelling for young learners, it is essential for teachers to effectively utilize this method in fostering moral values in early childhood education (Lee & Ying, 2019).

Based on the collection of 27 previous studies, a diagram was constructed to analyse the sample age groups covering education levels from preschool to university. The analysis revealed that more studies focused on preschool-aged samples, with a total of 11 articles. This was compared to 7 articles focusing on primary school-aged samples and 9 articles covering other categories.

The following diagram illustrates the sample age analysis based on the findings of these studies:

Analisis Tahap Peringkat Pendidikan Sampel Kajian

Figure 2. Diagram of Sample Education Level Analysis

This analysis indicates that preschool children were frequently selected as samples in storytelling education studies, with many researchers focusing on studies involving preschool-aged children.

The greater emphasis on preschool studies may stem from the recognition that the preschool stage is critical in early childhood development. At this stage, children are more inclined to absorb and internalize values conveyed through storytelling. However, it is also important to note the need for more studies focusing on primary and secondary education levels to understand the effectiveness of storytelling at different educational stages (Munn et al., 2018).

The impact of this trend suggests that although significant attention has been given to preschool education, there remains a lack of studies at other educational levels. This highlights the need for more balanced research that includes all educational levels, ensuring that the benefits of storytelling can be fully applied throughout the education system (Petticrew & Roberts, 2006).

4.3 Analysis of Article Objectives

From all the reviewed previous research articles, the findings indicate positive developments across various aspects. These articles can be categorized into four main categories, namely academic, affective, health, and cultural.

Table 3. Analysis of Article Objective

Research Objective	Article Numbers
Academic	3, 6, 7, 9, 10, 15, 16, 18, 19, 21, 22, 24, 25
Affective	2, 5, 8, 17, 23, 26
Health	4, 13
Cultural	1, 11, 12, 14, 20, 27

- *Academic Outcomes*

Within the academic outcomes category, a study by Wu and Chen (2020) highlights the use of a storytelling approach in science education for children. This study emphasizes the development of learning skills, research skills, and academic performance in children. Storytelling helps create an engaging learning environment and stimulates children’s interest in science. By incorporating storytelling elements, children can better grasp complex scientific concepts and relate them to their personal experiences. Additionally, a study by Walan and Enochsson (2019) examines the effectiveness

of a model that integrates storytelling and drama in teaching science to preschool children. This approach aims to enhance children's understanding of scientific concepts through an interactive and emotionally engaging experience. By utilizing dramatic and narrative elements, children become more involved in the learning process and acquire deeper knowledge. Both studies demonstrate that the storytelling approach, whether directly implemented or combined with dramatic elements, makes a significant contribution to the academic development of children, particularly in the context of science education. Through storytelling, children can acquire knowledge more effectively and experience positive improvements in their academic achievements.

- *Affective Outcomes*

In the category of affective outcomes, the study by Halimah et al. (2020) highlights the effectiveness of practical learning measures involving storytelling in instilling moral values and shaping positive responses in children. This study outlines several learning strategies aimed at reinforcing moral values such as honesty, patience, and empathy through storytelling experiences. The practical learning measures include the introduction of themes and character stories, the introduction of Wayang Golek figures, the storytelling process, discussions on character education depicted in the stories, and reflective activities on children's character development. By using this approach, children are not only passively engaged in listening to stories but are also given the opportunity to experience and internalize the moral values conveyed through the stories. This study emphasizes that storytelling functions not only as a medium for delivering moral messages to children but also as an effective tool in shaping attitudes, motivation, and positive emotional responses. Through interactive and immersive storytelling experiences, children can understand and apply moral values in their daily lives, as well as develop more positive relationships within their learning environment.

- *Health Outcomes*

In the health outcomes category, a study conducted by Türkyılmaz et al. (2022) examined the impact of digital storytelling about healthy eating on the health and eating behaviour of primary school pupils. This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of digital storytelling in shaping understanding and healthy eating practices among primary school children. The findings indicate that the intervention using digital storytelling had a positive impact on the pupils involved. Researchers found a significant improvement in the group of pupils who participated in the intervention compared to the control group. This means that digital storytelling successfully raised awareness about healthy eating and influenced their eating behaviours. The significant improvement in understanding and healthy eating behaviour among the participating pupils demonstrates that digital storytelling is an effective tool for promoting health awareness among primary school children. In this way, digital storytelling not only provides information about healthy eating but also motivates pupils to adopt better eating habits in their daily lives. This has positive implications for pupils' health and helps in the development of healthy eating habits from an early age.

- *Cultural Outcomes*

In the category of cultural outcomes, the study conducted by Tzima et al. (2020) highlights the crucial role of digital storytelling in acquiring new knowledge and fostering preschool children's interest in specific cultural aspects. This study aims to investigate the impact of digital storytelling in enhancing children's knowledge and interest in cultural elements presented in digital stories. The findings reveal that digital storytelling has made a significant contribution to strengthening preschool children's understanding of cultural aspects. In this way, digital stories effectively serve as an educational tool for conveying messages about culture to children. Not only do children enjoy the

digital storytelling experience, but they also develop a high level of interest in learning and understanding the cultural aspects presented. Additionally, the study found that digital storytelling fosters children's interest in cultural heritage and traditions represented in these digital narratives. This indicates that digital storytelling functions not only as an educational tool but also as an effective medium for transmitting cultural values to younger generations. Thus, the study emphasizes the importance of using technology to preserve and promote cultural heritage among young learners. Digital storytelling not only provides children with the opportunity to explore and understand their own culture but also broadens their awareness of cultural diversity worldwide. This plays a significant role in fostering cultural awareness, bridging gaps between different ethnic groups, and promoting international understanding and tolerance.

In summary, for the academic category, a total of 13 articles were selected, focusing on aspects of learning skill development, research, and academic performance within the teaching and learning context. These include the use of storytelling to enhance comprehension, experience-based learning, and the development of critical and analytical thinking skills among pupils.

Meanwhile, in the affective category, six articles were included, emphasizing pupils' attitudes, including motivation, confidence, and empathy. The focus is on how storytelling influences pupils' emotional responses and attitudes toward learning, particularly how storytelling helps instill moral values and elicit positive responses from children.

For the health category, only two articles were selected, where the impact of storytelling on children's physical health and eating habits was fully examined. These studies explore how storytelling can be used to communicate health messages and influence eating behavior among preschool and primary school children.

Lastly, in the cultural category, six articles were selected, focusing on cultural aspects, values, and traditions conveyed through storytelling. These studies examine how storytelling, particularly in digital form, can be used to transmit knowledge about cultural heritage to children and nurture their interest in specific cultural aspects.

Overall, this analysis demonstrates that storytelling not only has a positive impact on pupils' academic, affective, and health-related development but also plays a crucial role in strengthening their understanding and appreciation of culture and cultural heritage.

5. DISCUSSION

Based on the analysis of article publication years, it was found that the number of published articles increased from 2018 to 2021, peaking in 2018 and 2021. This trend may reflect a growing interest and awareness of storytelling techniques in the educational context during these years. The increase in article publications also indicates that more researchers focused on studying the effectiveness of storytelling in classrooms, making it an increasingly relevant topic in the field of education (Munn et al., 2018). However, the decline in the number of articles in 2022 and 2023 may be attributed to various factors, including researchers shifting their focus to other topics or changes in publication priorities (PRISMA, 2024).

An analysis of the sample articles shows that most research has focused on preschool children, while fewer studies have been conducted on primary school children. This highlights a research gap that needs to be addressed. Research on storytelling techniques at the primary school level is crucial, as this period is a critical phase in children's educational development (Nguyen & Nguyen, 2021).

Therefore, more extensive and comprehensive studies at this level could provide a better understanding of the effects of storytelling techniques on children's cognitive and emotional development.

The analysis of the purpose of the articles indicates that storytelling has a positive impact on various aspects, including academic, affective, health, and cultural dimensions (Robin, 2016). From an academic perspective, storytelling helps enhance the understanding of complex and abstract concepts, making them easier for children to grasp. Studies also show that storytelling can shape positive attitudes and values such as empathy, cooperation, and honesty among children (Gachago et al., 2014). This positive affective impact is essential for children's social and emotional development.

From a health perspective, stories containing health-related messages can influence children's health behaviours, such as adopting healthy eating habits and practicing personal hygiene (Nguyen & Nguyen, 2021). However, it was found that research in the health domain remains limited, indicating the need for more studies in this area. Future research could explore how storytelling techniques can be used in health education to promote healthy lifestyles among children.

The cultural aspect also demonstrates that storytelling helps children recognize and appreciate their cultural heritage. Storytelling can be used as a tool to instil pride in one's own culture and enhance understanding of the cultural diversity around them. This is crucial for fostering a more inclusive and tolerant society (Munn et al., 2018).

Future research recommendations include examining how storytelling can stimulate and strengthen creativity skills among children (Nguyen & Nguyen, 2021). This research could investigate the relationship between storytelling and children's ability to create their own stories, use their imagination, and express themselves through storytelling media. Additionally, the effectiveness of storytelling in STEM learning could be explored, particularly in facilitating the understanding of complex scientific concepts. This research could examine various ways in which storytelling elements can be integrated into the STEM curriculum to enhance pupils' interest and achievement in this field (Munn et al., 2018).

6. CONCLUSION

Overall, the systematic literature review on teaching children through storytelling techniques in the classroom demonstrates that storytelling plays a crucial role in the holistic development of children across various aspects of life. Storytelling not only enhances the understanding of academic concepts but also strengthens critical thinking, analytical, and research skills among children. Through storytelling, children can internalize moral values and develop positive attitudes such as motivation, self-confidence, and empathy. Additionally, storytelling can be used as a medium to convey health messages to children, influencing their eating habits and promoting positive health behaviours.

Lastly, storytelling enables children to recognize and appreciate their cultural heritage while fostering an interest in specific cultural aspects. Therefore, educators and education experts must acknowledge the power of storytelling as an effective tool in children's education. The use of well-planned and creative storytelling strategies can have a significant positive impact on children's holistic development in various educational and learning contexts.

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